

Impact of COVID19 on low income people in Bangladesh

Abstract:

The low-income people miserably affected for driving into workless situation due to current covid19 pandemic situation. Lockdown situation leads their life to traumatized situation due to having very much limited scope of earning money. The discussion on this issue prioritized in different print and electronic media. Different research organizations and government organizations conducted special study and published the results in print and electronic media. The published results on this topic have been rearranged to give a short overview to readers for understanding the reality of low-income people sufferings due to covid19 pandemic situation. Expert suggestion put in this article to sort out the way of mitigating the low-income people sufferings. Fact story included in this article with reference as for burning example. In a survey shows that the survey said that some 40% of the poor population and 35% of the vulnerable non-poor have already reduced their food consumption to cope with the situation amid the pandemic. The average income in the slums of Bangladeshi cities and among the rural poor has dropped by more than 80% since the outbreak of the novel coronavirus. The figure claimed the much discussion on this topic.

Introduction:

The world economy is blocked today by the impact of the corona. The great recession is approaching. It is feared that the magnitude of the great depression could be worse than the Great Depression of 1920. The black mark of worry is evident on the foreheads of the heads of government of the world's largest and strongest economies. It is as much about the number of covid-19 victims and the resulting death rate, as much as the threat of a great recession in the economy. Anxiety is not less for a middle-income economy like Bangladesh, but a multifaceted one. Following the prevailing lockdown thesis of corona tackling, it is said that the entire economy is blocked today without agricultural production.^[1] According to a survey conducted by the Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics in September 2020, the coronavirus epidemic has reduced the income per family by an average of BDT 4,000 per family. At this time of epidemic, the amount of food intake has come down to 52 per cent of households due to low income. Economic

activity started in Bangladesh, but many could not go to the previous level. Experts say that the decline in income and food intake of people across the country for more than six months will have a long-term impact. The lower income people are mostly sufferer in Bangladesh due to decrease their income sharply. Low income people mostly involve with informal sector like transport sector, micro street shop, saloon, restaurant, and some involve with formal sector like readymade garments sectors. COVID19 deadly affected to these low-income people livelihoods due to stalemate of movement. The low-income people are getting poorer. According to a survey by the private research firm South Asian Network on Economic Modelling (SANEM), the rate of poor increased to 42 per cent in last year's (2020) lockdown. A Bangladesh Institute of Development Studies (BIDS) survey last year (2020) also showed that 16.4 million people in the country have become poorer. According to the Centre for Policy Dialogue (CPD) survey, poverty increased to 35 percent at that time. Power and Participation Research Centre (PPRC) and BRAC Institute of Governance and Development (BIGD) said the poverty rate increased to 43 per cent. According to a BRAC survey, many of the low income were off during last year's (2020) general holiday. And after the normal holidays, their income decreases by up to 75 percent.[\[2\]](#)

Methodology:

COVID19 pandemic situation analysis in term of suffering the low-income people is a long discussion matter. Various financial institution, research organization and government organizations conducted different special study on this. This type of study is still continuing. As a result, established sources reference use is very logical in that writing. For this reason, secondary published data and expert opinion have taken consideration to complete this write up. The reference link marked with reference number of each section through creating hyperlink. The different acronyms elaborated in the different section of this article. The purified thought, data, analysis, expert opinions fully applied with reference in this article so that readers get reliability and comfort.

Miserable story - The way income has gone down

Jeevan Sharma, an employee of the men's haircut in Dhaka, was changing television channels. The chairs are all empty inside because there are no customers. Jeevan

Sharma, who has been in the profession for thirty years, says his income was around BDT 100 a day on October 6. Where his income before the coronavirus epidemic started was BDT 2,000 per day. In all, my shop has not been unlocked for three and a half months. The shop hasn't run yet. We didn't get a guest for at least two more months after the shop opened. The same is the case so far. No one has entered since this morning. There's food, there's a shop rent, but I'm earning only a hundred BDT yesterday. " Jeevan Sharma's joint family consists of 19 members but two earning. He says that eating and wearing in the family must be done anyway. He says, "Whether it is borrowed or something that has been accumulated earlier, the family does not stop eating with it. My family spends over BDT 30,000 a month. But I am in such a state that coronavirus does not earn even BDT 30. The money deposited in the hand was deposit pension scheme, which was all over. " [\[3\]](#)

Overall scenario of decreased the income level of low-income people:

According to published survey in April 2020, the average income in the slums of Bangladeshi cities and among the rural poor has dropped by more than 80% since the outbreak of the novel coronavirus, according to a survey report released on Friday. "A total of 63 per cent of such population, including day laborers, bhangari [plastic] workers, restaurant workers, maids, transport workers, agriculture laborers, construction and factory workers, petty businessmen, shop assistants and rickshaw pullers became economically inactive during the time," said the survey findings. The survey was jointly conducted by two independent local research centres -- the Power and Participation Research Centre and BRAC Institute of Governance and Development -- and included 5,471 households in urban slums and rural areas earlier in April 2020. Currently, over 3,300 slums in the capital Dhaka house around 646,000 people, mostly comprising of poor day laborers and rickshaw drivers, while more than 70% of the country's 165 million people live in rural areas. Of the total population, 20% live under the poverty line, according to government data. The survey said that some 40% of the poor population and 35% of the vulnerable non-poor have already reduced their food consumption to cope with the situation amid the pandemic. It added that per capita income in the slums had dropped by 82% to 27 Bangladeshi takas (\$0.32) during the survey week from 108 takas

(\$1.30) in February 2020, while per-capita income among the rural poor declined by 79% to 33 takas (\$0.39) from 89 takas (\$1.05).[\[4\]](#)

Economists say daily wage earners, labourers and the lower-class people are the worst hit by such lockdowns. Especially those who live on the outskirts of the city and the city. In this situation, people in the informal sector, including rickshaw pullers, transporters, hawkers, daily wagers, cleaners, workers, potters, fishermen, tailors, various types of masons, construction workers, and people depending on their daily income are not getting a chance to work. Van drivers, wheelbarrows, masons, carpenters, lock-key masons, bicycle vans, rickshaws and motor garage workers also have to stay away from work. Mobile recharge traders, flower vendors, shop employees and pavement traders are also being deprived of income. Milk traders in the village are not buying milk as sweet shops and bakeries are closed. The printing and publishing sector employees are already sitting unemployed. Slum dwellers in the city - who work as daily wagers in housing, construction sector and other fields, do hawkers and set up temporary shops on the roadside - are also unemployed now. The lockdown is having a negative impact on low income people in agriculture, industry and services as a whole. In addition to the food crisis, such people are also at risk of a major deterioration in health and mental conditions as a result of losing their income and sitting jobless.

Expert opinion to combat the downturn income of low-income people:

Abu Ahmed, an economist at the University of Dhaka, told Anadolu Agency that the government must partially withdraw the countrywide lockdown after April 25, the deadline of the existing shutdown. "Our economy is not strong like the European or Western countries and without a functioning the economy we are unable to provide relief to such a huge amount of people for long," Ahmed said. He added: "If the existing full lockdown extends further, it will exhaust the country's food reserves. So, the government should use its full efforts to maintain social distancing and partially lift the lockdown so that poor people can earn their livelihood." "[Otherwise] our reserve fund will be finished, the price of the [U.S.] dollar against the local currency will be increased and there is the risk that huge numbers of poor people will die due to starvation," warned Ahmed.[\[5\]](#)

In such a context economists have advised the poor to ensure food security during lockdown. They say social security programmes for the poor of the city have to be increased. At the same time, the rich must be motivated to help. Lockdown- They are talking about creating an environment where such people can earn easily in the aftermath. Experts say the government's programme must be implemented in full at the earliest. But this action of the government is not adequate. Because the government is getting the support of some people who are already registered with the government as poor and poor in many ways. But those who do not have information about the crisis do not have access to help. The poor population in the country has increased during last year's general holiday. Some of them have improved but a fresh lockdown has led many to return to the list of poor. The government needs to increase its support for such people, especially in cash. [\[6\]](#)

Conclusion:

COVID19 pandemic is still ongoing across the country as third wave now. Experts could not predict how many waves may come during covid19 pandemic. But experts' stresses on vaccination program for ensuring the coverage of all the country's people. The people income badly affected as a whole. The most sufferers are the low-income people. Some of their income source is almost closed and some of their income source fully closed. The over rate anxiousness creates paramount depression among the low-income people. Different organizations conducted survey and published results at policy level in order to draw the worsen situation of low-income people. The government has taken some initiative to alleviate the sufferings of low-income people. But experts opined that the initiative of government is not enough, and the government should increase the social safety net program activities countrywide with inclusiveness. Even some experts suggested to transfer the cash money among the low income people through mobile banking system where the local government active role is vital in all aspect of alleviating the suffering.

References:

The six references have taken from different prominent newspaper web sites that hyperlink created with each number of references in different sections.

About the Author:

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